

The Effect of Position Transfers and Awards on Employee Performance with Motivation as an Intervening Variable at PT. Jasa Raharja Surabaya Branch

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Abstract:- In this study, a work motivation variable will be added as an intervening variable in testing the effect of job transfers and awards given to employees, motivation of course requires employees who have good performance who work effectively and efficiently. This study aims: To analyze the effect of job transfers directly on the performance of employees at PT. Jasa Raharja Surabaya Branch. This study uses a survey method with a questionnaire as the primary data collector. The population is all employees, totaling 61 employees of PT. Jasa Raharja Surabaya, as for the method using the Proportional Stratified Rdbdom Sampling technique, this technique is used because the population is not homogeneous determined by the Taro Yaname formula and the Slovin formula. so that a sample of 61 respondents will be obtained. The data analysis technique used is partial least square (PLS). The results of the study concluded that; job mutations have a non-significant effect on employee performance; awards have been proven to have a significant positive effect on employee performance; job mutations have a non-significant effect on employee performance through motivation; rewards have a significant positive effect on employee performance through motivation.

Keywords:- Position Transfer; Award; Work Motivation and Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources in the organization have a very important role and function for the achievement of organizational goals, human resources here include all humans in the organization, namely those who are involved in the operational activities of the organization from the lowest level to the top (top management).). Human resources have a goal to improve the performance of an agency, so the formation of human resources who have the ability and skills is a must. In the world of work, there is often intense competition that is owned by employees and is required to continue to increase. By evaluating employee performance, it will be known whether the employee deserves to be improved. Carrying out a series of performance improvements is very necessary in order to always improve the quality of these employees so that the agency can grow and excel in the competition.

Human resources are currently the most important part in an organization or company. Human resource management is a human management process, through planning, recruitment, selection, training, development, compensation, safety and health careers as well as maintaining industrial relations until termination of employment to achieve company goals [1]. Human resource management is the recruitment, selection, development, maintenance, and use of human resources to achieve both individual goals and organizational goals [2].

Mutation is a common and routine activity in an organization. Mutation in a broad sense can be interpreted as a process of changing the employment status of an employee, whether caused by a transfer of assignment, changes in marital status, birth of children, promotions and so on [3]. Mutation is the activity of the company's leadership to move employees from one job to another job that is considered equal or equal [4]. Mentions mutation as the process of moving employees from one position to another, whether they are still in one area or in a different area. The narrower the span of control of the organization, then the effect caused by this mutation is relatively smaller, on the contrary, the wider the span of control of an organization, the greater the influence [5].

Reward means a reward, prize, award or reward. One of the ways in the management concept to improve the performance of its employees is by giving rewards. appreciation is an effort to foster a feeling of being accepted (recognized) in the work environment, which touches on aspects of compensation and aspects of the relationship between workers with one another [6]. This method will usually make employees do a good deed repeatedly and make a person's behavior or behavior and actions happy. Awards can also be a motivation to improve achievement, which can be achieved by someone who is active in work. Rewards and punishments affect employee performance [7].

Motivation is the provision of a driving force that creates one's work enthusiasm so that they want to work together, work effectively and be integrated with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction [8]. Motivation is a factor that encourages people to act in a certain way. The work motivation that exists in a person will manifest a behavior that is directed at the goal of achieving the target of satisfaction and is a group problem in the organization. In

fact, the problem of employee motivation in the General Section of PT. Jasa Raharja Surabaya is still far away. It is hoped that there will still be problems related to work motivation, such as; there are several employees who are less enthusiastic in working and to immediately do the work so that it can be quickly resolved; there are still debates and differences of opinion among employees in completing work; The existence of a authoritarian attitude that is owned by each individual employee, especially those who have high positions; Lack of employees who are given job education and training.

Achievement is an employee's demonstrated job performance, the ability of a person (employee) to produce, teach, or accomplish something. Performance reflects how successfully employees perform their duties. The higher the employee's performance, the more productive the company is [9]. The low performance of employees can be seen from the lack of cooperation between employees with one another. Some of the employees seen in the observations made carried out in November and December, where it was found that there were employees who were absent from work. This is the lack of ability of employees to understand each other's job descriptions. Usually occurs in employees who have just been transferred or who have just entered. In an effort to complete work, there are still those who do not have high initiative in completing their work and there are still employees who must be ordered by their superiors first. So that in its completion it hinders the achievement of targets set by the agency.

The phenomenon that occurs in PT. Jasa Raharja Surabaya indicates the existence of low employee performance. This is indicated by the presence of employees who arrive late and are absent as seen in the recapitulation data of lateness and vacant absences / absenteeism. From the data above, it shows that there are still employees who have delays and vacant absences or absenteeism that occurs from January to December 2021. This of course can have negative impacts on the company.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

The notion of the object of research is an attribute or nature or value of people, objects or activities that have certain variations that are determined by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions [10]. The objects in this study are mutations, rewards and work motivation of employees at PT. Jasa Raharja (Persero) Surabaya.

The population in this study were all employees of PT. Jasa Raharja includes branch heads, division heads, sub-section heads, heads of representatives and staff. The sample in this study, using the Proportional Stratified Random Sampling technique, this technique is used because the population is not homogeneous. In this study the number of indicators is 14 with parameter 4. So the sample used is 61 respondents. Instruments in the study used interviews, face-to-face and online using google form.

This model is a multivariate analysis technique that can test the relationship between variables and in the end a comprehensive picture is obtained from the whole Partial Least Square (PLS) model is a powerful method that does not assume data with a certain scale, and a relatively large number of samples. small. PLS is also used to confirm the theory [11]. PLS measurement model was developed as a general method for calculating or estimating the path model using latent variables with multiple indicators.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Validity Test Results

Outer Loadings					
Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-Values					
	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
X1.1 < MUTASI JABATAN (X1)	0.636	0.627	0.098	6.501	0.000
X1.2 < MUTASI JABATAN (X1)	0.714	0.711	0.082	8.745	0.000
X1.3 < MUTASI JABATAN (X1)	0.540	0.520	0.124	4.361	0.000
X1.4 < MUTASI JABATAN (X1)	0.799	0.791	0.062	12.957	0.000
X1.5 < MUTASI JABATAN (X1)	0.851	0.853	0.044	19.286	0.000
X1.6 < MUTASI JABATAN (X1)	0.838	0.836	0.044	19.137	0.000
X2.1 < PENGHARGAAN (X2)	0.755	0.753	0.055	13.670	0.000
X2.2 < PENGHARGAAN (X2)	0.863	0.867	0.034	25.518	0.000
X2.3 < PENGHARGAAN (X2)	0.892	0.890	0.037	24.240	0.000
Y1 < KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.799	0.795	0.051	15.561	0.000
Y2 < KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.506	0.520	0.135	3.753	0.000
Y3 < KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.757	0.762	0.069	10.959	0.000
Y4 < KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.800	0.798	0.054	14.875	0.000
Y5 < KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.663	0.647	0.107	6.166	0.000
Z1 < MOTIVASI (Z)	0.880	0.875	0.035	24.937	0.000
Z2 < MOTIVASI (Z)	0.862	0.857	0.043	19.875	0.000
Z3 < MOTIVASI (Z)	0.835	0.830	0.045	18.461	0.000

Table 1: Outer loading (factor loading) indicator with Dimension

A factor loading is the correlation between an indicator and a variable, if greater than 0.5 and/or p-value = significant, then the indicator is valid and an indicator/measure of the variable.

Based on the outer loading table above, the Loading Factor shown in the original sample number (eg for the indicator on the Position Mutation variable (X1), X1.1 = 0.636; X1.2 = 0.714; X1.3 = 0.540; X1.4 = 0.799; X1.5 = 0.851; X1.6 = 0.838 > 0.5 then it meets convergent validity. The results of the analysis in the table above show that all indicators in the research variables are Job Transfer, Reward, Motivation and Employee Performance variables. has a loading factor > 0.5, then the indicator meets convergent validity.

Based on the outer loading table above, the significance value (p-value) on Factor Loading (load factor) for the indicator on the variable Position Mutation (X1), for the indicator X1.1 = 0.000; X1.2 = 0.000; X1.3 = 0.000; X1.4 = 0.000; X1.5 = 0.000; X1.6 = 0.000 is smaller than 0.05, so it meets convergent validity. The results of the analysis show that all indicators in the research variables, namely variables, Position Transfers, Awards, Motivation and Employee Performance, are significant, because the p-value < 0.05 then the indicator meets convergent validity.

B. Discriminant Validity

Construct Validity	
	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.509
MOTIVASI (Z)	0.738
MUTASI JABATAN (X1)	0.545
PENGHARGAAN (X2)	0.703

Table 2: Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Results

A factor loading is the correlation between an indicator and a variable, if greater than 0.5 and/or p-value = significant, then the indicator is valid and an indicator/measure of the variable.

The next measurement model is the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value, i.e. the value indicates the magnitude of the indicator variance contained by the latent variable. Convergent AVE value greater than 0.5 also indicates a good adequacy of validity for latent variables. On the reflective indicator variable, it can be seen from the Average variance extracted (AVE) value for each construct (variable). A good model is required if the AVE value of each construct is greater than 0.5. The test results show that the AVE value for the (variable) construct of Position Transfer, Reward, Motivation and Employee Performance has a value greater than 0.5, so it is valid.

C. Composite Reliability

Construct Reliability			
	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability
KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.760	0.800	0.835
MOTIVASI (Z)	0.823	0.823	0.894
MUTASI JABATAN (X1)	0.831	0.852	0.875
PENGHARGAAN (X2)	0.790	0.814	0.876

Table 3: Composite Reliability Results

The reliability of the construct is measured by the composite reliability score, when the composite reliability score is higher than 0.70, the construct is reliable, and the indicator is considered to be consistent when measuring the latent variable.

The test results show that the composite reliability score of the constructs (variables) of job transfer, reward, motivation and employee performance is greater than 0.7. so reliable.

D. Structural Model

R Square		
	R Square	R Square Adjusted
KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.701	0.685
MOTIVASI (Z)	0.449	0.430

Table 4: R² (R-Square)

R² value (On Motivation) = 0.449 This can be interpreted that the model is able to explain the phenomenon / problem of motivation by 44.90%. While the rest (55.10%) is explained by other variables (other than Position Transfers, and Awards), which have not been included in the model and errors. This means that motivation is influenced by, position mutations, and awards, amounting to 44.90% while 55.10% is influenced by variables other than, position mutations, and awards.

R² value (on employee performance) = 0.701. This can be explained as the model is able to explain 70.10% of the employee performance phenomena/issues. The rest (29.90%) was explained by other variables (besides Position Transfer, Awards, and Motivation) which have not been included in the model and errors. This means that employee performance is influenced by, job mutations, awards, and motivation by 70.10% while 29.90% is influenced by variables other than job transfers, awards, and motivations.

E. PLS Model Analysis

Fig. 1: PLS Model Analysis Results

Based on the PLS output image above, it can be seen the magnitude of the factor loading value of each indicator which is located above the arrow between variables and indicators, it can also be seen the magnitude of the path coefficient which is above the arrow line between exogenous variables and endogenous variables. In addition, it can also be seen the size of the R-square which is right in the circle of endogenous variables (Employee Performance Variable (Y)).

F. Hypothesis Test

Path Coefficients					
Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-Values					
	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
MOTIVASI (Z) > KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.672	0.675	0.073	9.249	0.000
MUTASI JABATAN (X1) > KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.035	0.029	0.128	0.277	0.782
MUTASI JABATAN (X1) > MOTIVASI (Z)	0.207	0.243	0.159	1.303	0.193
PENGHARGAAN (X2) > KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.196	0.209	0.096	2.046	0.041
PENGHARGAAN (X2) > MOTIVASI (Z)	0.503	0.481	0.141	3.565	0.000

Table 5: Path Coefficient Results

According to the internal weight test results in Table 5 above, it can be concluded that the effect of position mutation on employee performance is not significant, and the path coefficient is 0.035, of which p value = 0.193 is greater than = 0.05 (5%); the position mutation of motivation has a significant effect on motivation. Insignificant effect with a path coefficient of 0.207 with p-value = 0.193 greater than a value of = 0.05 (5%); reward has a significant positive effect on employee performance with a path coefficient of 0.196 with p-value = 0.041 with a value less than Value = 0.05 (5%); Reward has a significant positive effect on motivation with a path coefficient of 0.503, where p-value = 0.000 is less than value = 0.05 (5%); Motivation has a significant positive effect on employee performance , the path coefficient is 0.672, where p-value = 0.000 is less than the value of = 0.05 (5%).

G. Intervening Variable

Total Indirect Effects					
Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-Values					
	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
MUTASI JABATAN (X1) > MOTIVASI (Z) > KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.139	0.165	0.111	1.253	0.211
PENGHARGAAN (X2) > MOTIVASI (Z) > KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.338	0.322	0.096	3.531	0.000

Table 6: Intervening Variable

It can be seen from the above table that the effect of position change on employee performance through incentives is not significant, and the path coefficient is 0.139, where p value = 0.211 is greater than the value of = 0.05 (5%); incentives have a significant impact on employee performance through incentives. Positive effect, the path coefficient is 0.338, where p-value = 0.000 is less than the value of = 0.05 (5%).

H. Intervening Variable

Total Indirect Effects					
Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-Values					
	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
MUTASI JABATAN (X1) > MOTIVASI (Z) > KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.139	0.165	0.111	1.253	0.211
PENGHARGAAN (X2) > MOTIVASI (Z) > KINERJA PEGAWAI (Y)	0.338	0.322	0.096	3.531	0.000

Table 6: Intervening Variable

As can be seen from the above table, the effect of position change on employee performance through incentives is not significant, and the path coefficient is 0.139, where the value of p-values = 0.211 is greater than the value of p-values = 0.05 (5%). ; Rewards have a significant positive effect on employee performance through motivation, with a path coefficient of 0.338, where p-value = 0.000 is less than a value of = 0.05 (5%).

I. The Effect of Position Mutation on Employee Performance

Based on the statistical test above, the variable of job mutation has a non-significant effect on employee performance, where position mutation has a non-significant effect on employee performance with a path coefficient of 0.035 where the p-values = 0.193 is greater than the value of = 0.05(5%). This indicates that the higher the employee mutation rate for PT. Jasa Raharja Surabaya will certainly improve employee performance as the employees of PT. Jasa Raharja Surabaya.

Based on the results of Hasibuan's analysis, 2016. As previously explained, job transfer is a change of place of work/position for employees within one organization. Because the transfer is sometimes necessary for employees or the company itself. The principle of mutation is to transfer employees to the right positions and appropriate jobs, so that their enthusiasm and work productivity increase.

So it can be concluded that the mutation must be based on several factors, one of which is in accordance with the wishes of the workforce concerned. If the worker concerned does not have the desire to be transferred, then there will be a forced mutation. The forced mutation will be able to cause a person's performance to decrease. As previously explained, performance is the result of the work of employees in order to achieve the goals of the company. The transfer will not reduce performance if the basis and

method of the transfer is applied or implemented correctly by the management.

J. *The Effect of Rewards on Employee Performance*

Based on the statistical test above, the award has a positive significant effect on employee performance, where Job Transfer to Motivation has a non-significant effect on motivation with a path coefficient of 0.207 where the p-values = 0.193 is greater than the value of = 0.05 (5%). This indicates that the level of appreciation is able to contribute to the performance of employees at PT. Jasa Raharja Surabaya.

The results of the analysis describe the performance appraisal, reward, and punishment on employee performance correlated well. The results of the research analysis simultaneously performance appraisal, reward and punishment, have a significant effect on employee performance. Partially performance appraisal, reward and punishment partially, have a significant effect on employee performance.

The result of the descriptive analysis is that both studies use reward and punishment as independent variables. While the difference with this study is that this study uses employee productivity as the dependent variable, but this study uses performance appraisal as an independent variable and employee performance as the dependent variable. In addition, the object of the location studied focuses on the convection industry company.

K. *The Effect of Position Mutation on Employee Performance With Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable.*

Based on the above statistical tests, the variable job mutation has a negligible effect on employee performance through incentives. This indicates that job change has an insignificant effect on employee performance through incentives, with a path coefficient of 0.139, with a p-value = 0.211 greater than a value of = 0.05 (5%).

The results of the company's research conducted job transfers to employees, basically, mutations are transferring employees to the right positions and appropriate jobs, so that their enthusiasm and work productivity increase, which aims to increase work efficiency and effectiveness within the company.

The purpose of the transfer is one of the follow-up actions taken from the results of the work motivation assessment which is expected to provide job descriptions, job characteristics, work environment, and work tools that are suitable for the employee concerned so that they can work efficiently and effectively in that position. Mutation or transfer of employees is very important and needs to be done, both in terms of the interests of employees and the interests of the company. A good mutation is a mutation that is in accordance with the applicable procedures in an organization, there is no discrimination, every employee is equal in the eyes of the leader. The implementation of job transfers provides work passion or work motivation to employees who excel or provides a level of teaching to employees who make mistakes from company regulations.

L. *Quality of Appreciation on Employee Performance With Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable.*

The following are the results of research conducted, regarding awards have a significant positive effect on employee performance through motivation. The award has a significant positive effect on employee performance through incentives, with a path coefficient of 0.338, where p-value = 0.000 is less than a value of = 0.05 (5%). Therefore, motivation acts as a mediating variable (because it can act as a mediator) on the effect of rewards on employee performance.

That the results of research if employees already feel the passion and enthusiasm from within themselves, automatically employees will be motivated to increase productivity and show the best performance at work. This will have a very good impact on the company, because productive employees will be able to help the company achieve its goals. There is an influence between rewards on work motivation. From the results of empirical studies, it is proven that intrinsic rewards have a positive and significant effect through motivation on employee performance.

IV. CONCLUSION

Position mutation does not contribute to employee performance. This suggests a higher employee mutation rate for PT. Of course, Jasa Raharja Surabaya lowered the performance of the PT staff. Jasa Raharja Surabaya; this award enhances PT's staff performance. Jasa Raharja Surabaya. This means that the award is a nexus of collaboration, job satisfaction, effective procurement, motivation, employee stability, discipline and influence from unions and government to motivate PT employee performance. Jasa Raharja Surabaya ; So far, job mutations have failed to boost employee performance through incentives. So say PT. Jasa Raharja Surabaya's failure to serve insurance participants with confidence, timeliness, accuracy and satisfaction, of course, reduces employee performance through incentives; incentives can promote employee performance through incentives. Thus, motivation acts as a mediating variable (because it is able to mediate) on the effect of rewards on employee performance at PT. Jasa Raharja Surabaya. While the suggestion is that PT. Jasa aharja Surabaya still maintains and even improves a culture of responsiveness, agility, and toughness as well as the motto "Prime in Protection, Excellence in Service"; The slogan "Indonesian Society Insurance", Company Quality Policy "Implementing an integrated work system by making the best quality a work culture to support efficient and productive company activities"; and still maintain significant variables and even have to be further improved.

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